

Workshop: Finding Love in Everyday Objects

Subtitle: How a product's personality connects with women

Agnete Enga • Carla Diana

**Smart Design*

New York, USA, Carla.diana@smartdesignworldwide.com

Abstract: In today's market, women influence more than 80% of purchases on products and services, yet many companies are struggling to connect with the female audience. A Consumer Electronics Association survey found that only 1% of women believe that consumer electronics brands have their needs in mind. [1] The Femme Den is a group within Smart Design dedicated to understanding and exploring opportunities in design and gender. We believe in creating products that offer people a rich emotional connection through a stronger focus on what we call the "warmer values". We are combining this knowledge with Human Robot Interaction research to develop techniques for uncovering meaningful attributes that can be expressed through product forms, behaviors and technology. In this workshop, participants will work in teams, exploring techniques for creating products to successfully connect with women on an emotional level, finding love through product personality.

Key words: *Design, emotional connection, attachment, warmer values, product behavior, consumer electronics, designing for gender, human robot interaction.*

1. Introduction

The women's market is a huge business opportunity. In a traditional family situation, women are often considered the "CEO of the household", and shop on behalf of their families. Women influence over 80% of all consumer purchasing decisions [2], however, women's real needs and values are often not taken into consideration in the design process. To capitalize on this market segment, companies must recognize the female perspective, and appeal to them with meaningful product experiences that offer real benefits. This experience must be then be delivered through an appropriate product's or service's personality, manifested through form, color, movement and interactive behaviors.

2. Designing for women

2.1. Consider women as a filter for great experiences for everyone

Over the last 30 years, a plethora of scientific studies in fields ranging from neuroscience through anthropology and linguistics have shown that from the foundation up, men and women are vastly different. Hormones influence how our brains are wired, and ultimately define our differences. Men and women communicate and process information differently, and the differences also lead them to view and interact with products differently. We see dramatic differences between the genders in emotions towards products.

Because of all the demands on their time with family, home and work, women are not as tolerant of time

consuming and unintuitive product experiences, which we see so often in consumer electronics. Men tend to be more forgiving and take a certain pride in the skill of mastering a product. Women tend to want it to work well right from the start. They see technology as a way to simplify their chaotic lives, and they want it all – great design, outstanding performance and an intuitive experience.

When starting a new project, it is important for product designers to ask a very fundamental question, “Is the product going to be used by men only, women only or by both?” Certain elements will be used by one gender only, which is when a “visible” approach is appropriate. We see this approach typically used when designing products linked to physical differences between men and women, such as shaving items and feminine hygiene products. However, when there is something that both genders use, women don’t want to be singled out as having special needs. In the case of driving a car, for example, women don’t want to be given the message that they need their own special car; that is stigmatizing. This is where the “transparent” approach comes into play. The key with the transparent design approach is to be inspired by women’s demanding needs, but use this inspiration to create solutions will be appreciated by men and women alike. We will explore this approach in our workshop as a key ingredient for success.

2.2. Warmer values

Historically, the consumer electronics industry has placed their focus on what the Femme Den calls “colder values”, slick styling and technical specifications focused on the machine. We know that to connect with women, we need to focus on personal meaning and an emotional connection, a space in which women tend to be comfortable, and what we call “warmer values” [4]. The study of Design and Emotion can be informed by the development of techniques that include an assessment of warmer values as part of the product design process. Our recent projects in gender have identified a number of characteristics in products that offer warmer values. They include:

- Fitting into a woman’s life: Women think about the larger implications for their families and are attracted by lifestyle improvements more than men are. The product itself is secondary.
- Technology for a reason: When looking at products out on the market we see a lot of technology just for technology’s sake, where companies have added a large number of features just because they can. But not all features add to the experience of using a product – in many cases they subtract.
- A celebration of the end-result: Females tend to be less enticed by the physical product itself, and more about the end result. For example, a product that makes her more efficient means that she can spend time on other things she cares more about.
- Product personality: It’s about taking advantage of all the fun and magical things you can do with technology to make the products come to life and have a personality of their own. That way it will earn affection and encourage the user to cherish it and kept it for a long time.

Figure. 2 Examples of “warmer values” in product design

2. Building warmer values through emotional attachment

2.1. Building attachment to an object

With the advent of more sophisticated product interactions, social relationships between people and products are becoming both deeper and more commonplace. The more interaction that we have with an object over time, the more “psychic energy” we build around it, and the more meaning it has for the user [5]. Since we have learned that having an enjoyable product is important for women, offering an engaging experience can encourage continued exploration and attachment.

2.2. New opportunities for making objects expressive

Advances in technology and the affordability of embedded sensors are enabling richer product experiences through the behavioral attributes a designer can bestow on a product. For example, devices can sense someone’s presence and respond with sound, light or movement to make products seem animated and “alive”. Designers can harness these characteristics to intentionally craft personalities that fit the vision of the brand and product.

2.3. We anthropomorphize everything

People often impart human characteristics on non-humans, such as reading human expressions from a pet’s behavior. A similar phenomenon occurs for objects when people (especially women) read emotions from the sounds and movements of automated products. For example, Roomba robotic vacuum cleaners inspire social interaction to the extent that people will name them and refer to them as “he” or “she”[6]. Amazon.com reviews of the Roomba 530 describe an incredible sense of wonder, attachment and anthropomorphizing.

When designing a new domestic robot for a client, the authors began by defining those moments where people might look to the device to express its self in order to best demonstrate a coherent and distinct personality. A focus on the warmer values led to a solution that could connect with women on all levels..

3. Workshop goals and intended outcomes.

The goal of the 3-hour workshop is to increase participants’ awareness of warmer values, and practice a transparent approach. They will explore knowledge about techniques for defining benefits, appropriate

technology, desired end results and product personality during the product development process. It is aimed at 10-15 participants who are interested in the conception of products or services. Intended outcomes are:

- Heightened awareness of the importance of warmer values
- An understanding of how gender influences how we view and value products
- An understanding of design methodologies used to craft product behavior
- A shared workshop experience for participants from a wide range of backgrounds

4 Workshop activities

4.1. Introduction

A presentation on how to design with gender in mind, the importance of warmer values, and case studies of products that through the transparent design approach successfully connect with both men and women.

4.2. Warm up: Break-up letter

The participants will be divided into groups of 3-4 and assigned a specific product category and challenge to solve. The first task is to describe the current experience in a “break-up letter” to that specific product / experience, which will help them highlight and share the main issues in a fun way.

4.3. Main exercise: Identifying personality traits and design opportunities

Each group will be asked to identify key moments in the interaction with the product (taking it out of the box, turning it on or off, getting a readout, etc.). They will then brainstorm product solutions that address those key moments with the warmer values in mind.

4.4. Workshop final activity: Co-creation design activity

They will identify existing product attributes and use them to design a new object, explaining how its personality might come through via physical or behavioral attributes, followed by presentations and discussions.

5. References

[1] Consumer Electronics Association. (2004).

[2] Barletta, Martha. (2003). *Marketing to Women: How to Understand, Reach and Increase Your Share of the World's Largest Market Segment*. Dearborn Trade Publishing.

[3] Sayre, Kate & Silverstein, Michael J. (2009). The Female Economy. *Harvard Business Review*.

[4] <http://www.femmeden.com/> , <http://www.smartdesignworldwide.com/>

[5] Csikszentmihályi, M., and E. Rochberg-Halton. (1981) *The Meaning of Things: Domestic Symbols and the Self*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

[6] Sung, J., Guo, L., Grinter, R.E., and Christensen, H.I. (2007). "My Roomba is Rambo": Intimate Home Appliances. *UbiComp 2007: Ubiquitous Computing*. Heidelberg: Springer Berlin.